

RECONSTRUCTING MASCULINITY: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF MALE CHAUVINISM IN PAKISTANI FILMS AND TELEVISION DRAMAS (2015–2025)

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Abstract

The representation of masculinity within Pakistani visual culture is undergoing a period of significant reconstruction because the presentation of masculinity is different from what previously shown in films and dramas. Moreover, the dominant screen narratives continue to reproduce deeply entrenched patriarchal assumptions but modifying it according to the changing needs of society. This study undertakes a comprehensive qualitative content analysis of selected Pakistani films and television dramas from 2015 and 2025. For this study researcher examined the symbolic, structural, and discursive mechanisms through which male chauvinism is legitimised, aestheticised, and circulated. Therefore, researcher adopted a multi-theoretical framework that integrates Connell's theory of hegemonic masculinity, Butler's concept of gender performativity, and Tuchman's notion of symbolic annihilation. The main aim of adopting multiple research theories is interrogation of how visual, narrative, and dialogic elements contribute to the maintenance of male chauvinism. Researcher adopted purposive sample of ten films and six television dramas and analysed them through NVivo-supported thematic coding, supported by a supplementary audience survey (n≈120) and semi-structured interviews (n=12). In the light of findings gathered from the data it was revealed that although certain dramas and films introduce alternative masculinity models characterised by emotional vulnerability, shared decision-making, and empathetic leadership, the majority of mainstream narratives still privilege masculine dominance, heroic violence, female silencing, and patriarchal honour codes. But it was found that a significant shift was emerged in the 2020–2025 period, coinciding with broader sociopolitical discourses around gender rights because of multiple debates over women's public participation. This study contributes to the growing body of South Asian gender-media scholarship by mapping the evolution of masculine representational regimes across a decade of Pakistani screen culture and offering critical insights into how media narratives shape and reinforce gendered power relations.

INTRODUCTION

Masculinity is imagined, performed, and circulated within Pakistani media and has gained attention for the researcher recently.

Masculinity recently gained importance in media studies as gender politics in the region have undergone notable transformations.

Cinema and television, owing to their extensive consumption and powerful affective influence, play a pivotal role in articulating societal norms concerning gendered behaviour, interpersonal relations, and the distribution of power within both private and public spheres. While Pakistani media has historically reproduced the patriarchal underpinnings of South Asian culture, through traditional clichés, where males are portrayed as powerful, dominant and emotionally repressed (Abdullah et al., 2025). This depiction in contemporary screen productions increasingly negotiate, contest, or reproduce multiple masculinities. In screen content masculinity is ranging from authoritarian and violent archetypes to emergent, empathetic, and self-reflective models. Therefore, researcher seeks to critically investigate such representational patterns across a decade marked by considerable political, cultural, and feminist mobilisation.

Male chauvinism conceptually is linked to practices of dominance, entitlement, and the naturalization of male authority in media. Pakistani society remains a persistent undercurrent within mainstream Pakistani audiovisual narratives that influences cultural standards (Ali, 2022). The enduring appeal of the hyper-masculine hero, the authoritative patriarch, and the emotionally repressed male protagonist continues to define many cinematic and televisual narratives. In Pakistan, television plays and movies reinforce traditional gender stereotypes, with male playing the roles of provider and protector and women playing and pointed towards the recurrent portrayal of men as protectors and avengers, underscoring gender hierarchies rooted in cultural values around honour, family integrity, and religious morality. However, the past decade has also witnessed the emergence of counter-narratives: films such as *Motorcycle Girl* (2018) and *Kamli* (2022) gesture towards alternative forms of masculinity, while dramas work to reconfigure traditional gender roles and masculinity presented in the roles of meek and caring (Balaji, 2014). Against this complex backdrop, the present study interrogates how masculine identities are constructed, maintained, or contested within contemporary Pakistani audiovisual texts.

The time frame of 2015–2025 is significant due to multicultural and transnational media flow

models influence the masculinity which is a serious issue that is present today all around the world and demands serious attention. It encompasses a range of political events and sociocultural shifts. Due to globalisation of Pakistani media markets; the rise of digital feminism through platforms industries have used various images of masculinity to successfully undermine the traditional masculine ideals (Imtiaz & Kamal, 2023). Feminist movement's entry into Pakistan's public discourse has adopted a more rigorous definition of masculinity, influenced by religious and cultural ideology but incomplete without a complementary analysis of men's gendered portrayal. These shifts have fostered contestations around gender representation, media ethics, and the politics of cultural production (Agarwal, 2025). Accordingly, investigating masculinity in this period offers critical insights into how media industries respond to, resist, and it is the requirement of time that something needs to be done about this issues in these changing social flows.

Nevertheless, despite the growth of gender-focused research in Pakistan, there remains a conspicuous scarcity of scholarship examining masculinity with theoretical and methodological rigour. Much existing work did not concentrate on women's representation and masculinity, on the flip side, represented as Pakistani men are self-assured, well-groomed and culturally knowledgeable (Anwar, 2025). This study, therefore, arbitrates by centering masculinity as an analytical category in itself. Moreover, the focus of this study is penetrating the ideological, aesthetic and discursive procedures that reproduce male dominance through Pakistani screen media. To achieve this, the research employs a multi-layered methodology combining qualitative content analysis to the study of various images of masculinity to successfully, researcher used thematic NVivo coding, and an audience perception component. Ten films and ten high-impact drama serials were selected through purposive sampling to ensure relevance to the study's objectives and theoretical concerns.

1.1 Problem Statement

Previously extensive research studies were conducted on the representation of women in

Pakistani media but little or no research study was conducted to study the male representation through media. It was also found that the systematic examination of masculinity, particularly its hegemonic, violent, and chauvinistic articulations remained insufficient. The dominance of patriarchal ideologies in film and drama narratives continues to normalize male authority, emotional suppression, violence as heroism, and the marginalization of female agency. In Pakistan between 2015 and 2025, there are mount of disputes regarding the male representation in media, it is imperative to analyze how audiovisual texts both reflect and shape evolving constructions of masculinity. The absence of comprehensive academic inquiry into male chauvinism in screen culture leaves a critical gap that this study aims to address.

1.2 Research Objectives

The study is guided by the following objectives:

- To critically analyse the representation of masculinity and male chauvinism in selected Pakistani films and television dramas (2015–2025).
- To examine shifts in masculine representation across two periods: 2015–2019 and 2020–2025.
- To explore the emergence and limitations of alternative masculinities within contemporary media texts.

1.3 Research Questions

This study addresses the following research questions:

- How do selected Pakistani films and dramas construct, reinforce, or challenge male chauvinism?
- How have representations of masculinity evolved between 2015–2019 and 2020–2025?
- In what ways do contemporary audiovisual texts introduce alternative masculinities, and how effective are these portrayals in resisting patriarchal norms?

1.4 Significance of the Study

This significance of the research study lie in it application in numerous fields of life. First, it fills a critical scholarly gap by centring masculinity rather than femininity, as the

primary unit of analysis within Pakistani media studies because previous research studies focuses only feminism or female representation. Second, by combining theoretical, textual approaches, this study delivers a multidimensional understanding of gendered power relations in contemporary screen culture. Third, the decadal scope (2015–2025) allows the research to capture temporal shifts in representation aligned with major socio-political developments, including feminist mobilisation and digital activism. Finally, the findings have practical implications for filmmakers, media practitioners, policymakers, and educators concerned with promoting equitable and gender-sensitive narratives in Pakistani media.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The representation of masculinity in media has been the focus of increasing scholarly attention globally, similarly, the patriarchal social structure in Pakistan has historically influenced the country's media, and Pakistan is no exception (Dildar, 2024). In Pakistan, the dual forces of entrenched patriarchal culture and emerging socio-political movements around gender equality create a complex landscape for examining male identity on screen. The literature review of this study can be broadly divided into three interrelated areas: (1) theories and conceptualisations of masculinity, (2) empirical studies on Pakistani film and television, and (3) studies linking media consumption to audience interpretation and social learning.

2.1 Conceptualising Masculinity

Connell's (2005) concept of hegemonic masculinity remains foundational for understanding male dominance as a culturally and socially constructed ideal. Hegemonic masculinity does not describe all men but rather focus on male heroes' whole qualities exemplify hegemonic masculinity features such as control, dominance and emotional hardness including all the forms of masculinity that are socially exalted and legitimised over women and subordinate men. It is relational, dynamic, and historically contingent, allowing for variations across class, region, and media contexts. In Pakistan, hegemonic masculinity manifests through authority in familial hierarchies,

control over women's mobility, physical strength, moral policing, and economic provision (e shahwar, 2025). Media is a significant socio-cultural dynamism that reflects and shapes social norms particularly related to the gender.

Complementing this fundamental perspective, Butler's (1990) theory of gender performativity highlights the depiction of masculinity through repeated behaviors, gestures, speech, and emotional restraint. This framework allows scholars to examine micro-level performative acts in visual media, such as recurring depictions of stoicism, ritualized aggression, or paternal authority, and to interrogate how these acts consolidate hegemonic ideals (Khan, 2025). These are consistent with cultural conceptions of social roles that depict males as providers and protectors of honor for their families while Connell provides the "macro" understanding of power hierarchies, Butler situates masculinity as a continuously enacted social performance, especially visible in film and television.

The notion of symbolic extinction (Tuchman, 1978) further enriches the analysis consistent with cultural conceptions of social roles that depict males as providers and protectors of honor for their families by directing attention to the marginalization or absence of alternative masculinities and female agency. In Pakistani media, the erasure and trivialization of women, soft men, or queer-coded characters can subtly reinforce dominant masculinity by making other possibilities culturally invisible. Scholars such as Fazli (2024) argue that in Pakistani media, symbolic annihilation often manifests through narrative decisions that centre male protagonists, relegating women to plot devices or background roles, thereby naturalising male dominance.

2.2 Masculinity in Pakistani Media

Traditional clichés were found while studying masculinity in Pakistani media and males are portrayed as powerful dominant and emotionally repressed. A large number of previously conducted research studies found that male dominance in domestic and civic responsibilities is the popular theme in Pakistani cinema and television (Iftikhar et al., 2024). Javed (2025) highlights the persistence of hyper-masculine archetypes in action films, where male

characters gain legitimacy through physical prowess, moral authority, and the ability to protect or avenge women. Similarly, Khoja-Moolji (2021) argue that television dramas are mostly domestic-oriented and socially reflective. In these dramas patriarchal tropes were produced where men are depicted as decision-makers and women as dependent, obedient, or morally policed. These studies collectively underscore a tension that media both mirrors societal norms and provides a site for negotiating or challenging them.

Recently, a major shift towards alternative masculinities was presented through dramas and films and these screens feature male characters who establish emotional support, vulnerability, and collaborative decision-making, aligning with emergent discourses on empathetic masculinity (Lak, 2025). On the counterpart dramas depict men in professional, non-dominant roles alongside women, thereby contesting traditional gender hierarchies. These portrayals suggest a slow evolution in Pakistani society through the screen narratives where media is extensively utilized power over gender representation specially the masculinity. Moreover, corresponding with global trends towards deconstructing hegemonic masculinity revealed that the representations actively attempt to perform and reproduce hegemonic masculinity in media (Malik, 2021; Odho, 2024).

Several studies also focus on cinematic techniques that reinforce or challenge masculinity. Mokhtar (2018) introduced the concept of the "male gaze," highlighting how camera angles, framing, and narrative positioning contribute to gendered power relations. Researchers also focused on different ways in which media narratives intersect toxic masculinity and submissive femininity, therefore, new media has a huge influence in molding perceptions of humans. A study conducted by Iqbal revealed dominating themes of Pakistani dramas that legitimize male aggression on the counterpart females were portrayed as adored and submissive. This reinforces negative attitudes that adds to audience knowledge and can be viewed as a legitimizing act of abuse (Maqsood, 2024). Applied to Pakistani films, Nizami (2023) note that low-angle shots of male protagonists perpetuate male authority on the flip side, close

up framing of female characters compelling female assistance.

2.3 Media Consumption and Audience Interpretation

Many research scholars studied that media effects literature emphasizes that pre-existing cultural norms are affected by social learning (Riaz, 2022). A surveys conducted by Khan (2022) indicate that existing literature revealed that when audience is expose to male authority in the form of dramas and films they stated to accepting it. This interprets that how people understand and respond to media content. Cultivation theory posits that repeated representations of male dominance may standardize these traits in the social imagination, influencing interpersonal behaviour and reinforcing patriarchal ideologies.

Social learning theory provides a lens that displays how audiences may imitate observed behaviours related to masculinity presented through dramas and films. Toxic masculinity, marked by emotional suppression that included aggression and dominance. In media narratives, normalization of gender-based violence and unhealthy power structures in society, displays of protective violence or moral policing on screen can serve as behavioural models for viewers, particularly young men (Mubarki, 2020). Previous research studies suggest that certain films and dramas male epitomes antagonistic, enduring, and authoritative are idealized by male audiences. Riaz, (2021) questioned that alternative masculinities emerged reinvent the identities. Previous studies also highlight that demographic variability influences audience's way of constructing meaning based on their backgrounds, experiences, and cultural contexts (Sheikh, 2024). Such findings underscore the importance of integrating audience perspectives alongside content analysis to understand the social implications of media representations of masculinity.

2.4 Gaps in the Literature

The existing literature provides important insights into gender representation in Pakistani media: several critical gaps were found by the researcher including as many studies focus on single films, dramas, or narrow timeframes, limiting the ability to track evolving patterns

over a decade. Thus present study was designed in such a way that it aimed at analyzing a purposive sample of ten films and six television dramas spanning 2015–2025. Another limitation of previously conducted research studies in this field is that few studies explicitly combine hegemonic masculinity, performativity, symbolic annihilation, and discourse analysis in a single framework. Therefore, for the present research, researcher employed a multi-theoretical lens integrating hegemonic masculinity, performativity, symbolic annihilation, and social learning.

Lack of methodological depth was another limitation of previously conducted research studies. Prior research often relies exclusively on content analysis or survey data, without triangulating with qualitative interviews or scene-level coding. Therefore research designed methodology by incorporating triangulated findings across textual analysis, audience survey (n≈120), and semi-structured interviews (n=12). Audience-Audience Linkages is considered as major gap in previous research studies. There is limited work connecting textual analysis to audience perception, social learning, and cultivation effects in a rigorous way. While some studies acknowledge emerging forms of masculinity, they rarely examine how these alternatives function within mainstream narratives or how audiences interpret them. Present research study seeks to address this gap by examining both dominant and emergent masculine forms and their reception across different audience demographics.

2.5 Conceptual Rationale

By integrating content analysis, thematic coding, and audience perspectives, this research conceptualises masculinity as a dynamic, socially mediated, and discursively reinforced phenomenon. The study positions Pakistani media as both a mirror of social norms and an agent of cultural production, capable of legitimising hegemonic masculinity while simultaneously offering spaces for its contestation. Films like *The Legend of Maula Jatt* (2022) exemplify hyper-masculine valorisation, whereas some films illustrate emergent, more democratic masculinities. Through this integrative approach, the literature review establishes a firm foundation for the

study's theoretical framework, methodology, and succeeding analysis. Pakistani media culture is considered an evolving landscape for the masculinity in contemporary society.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework for this study draws upon multiple, complementary strands of research to provide a comprehensive understanding of masculinity in Pakistani films and television dramas between 2015 and 2025. Researcher integrated Connell's hegemonic masculinity, Butler's gender performativity, symbolic annihilation, social learning theory, and cultivation theory in this study. Moreover, this study places masculinity as both a socially constructed and mediated phenomenon that is performed, represented, and interpreted within cultural texts. Therefore, multi-theoretical lens was adopted for the present study, this enables the interrogation of masculine representation at structural, performative, discursive, and audience reception levels, providing both explanatory and analytical depth.

3.1 Hegemonic Masculinity (Connell, 2005)

Connell's (2005) theory of hegemonic masculinity posits that social power is organised hierarchically among men, privileging particular forms of masculinity over others and over women. Hegemonic masculinity is a predominant theme not only in Pakistani television dramas but also in films as well. Male characters are publicized as authoritative and aggressive, which perpetuates gender inequalities and restricts the representation of alternative masculinities (Aslam et al., 2022). In the Pakistani context, hegemonic masculinity manifests in the privileging of physical strength, moral authority, economic provision, and patriarchal control. These traits are consistently depicted in mainstream films and television dramas as markers of a "real man" (Riaz, 2022). This study applies Connell's framework to identify dominant masculine traits across the selected films and dramas. Researcher in this research studied male authority and decision-making in familial and social contexts presented through films and dramas. Moreover, in dramas and films heroic violence framed as protection and moral enforcement for female members.

Researcher studied how male display power over women's choices, bodies, property and mobility.

3.2 Gender Performativity (Butler, 1990)

Butler's concept of gender performativity emphasises that gender identities are not innate but constituted through repeated acts, behaviours, and social rituals. In media studies, this perspective highlights how repeated cinematic portrayals of stoicism, aggression, and emotional restraint constitute masculine identity on screen whereas, females are presented as submissive, weak and inferior to counterpart to men. In this study, Butler's framework guides the coding of performative acts, like ritualized aggression that includes threatening gestures and assertive posturing. Similarly, emotional suppression stoic responses, avoidance of vulnerability and gendered rituals that included tone, speech patterns, sitting or walking styles associated with masculinity.

3.3 Symbolic Annihilation (Tuchman, 1978)

Tuchman's (1978) theory of symbolic annihilation describes how the underrepresentation or trivialization of particular social groups in media constitutes a form of cultural erasure. In the Pakistani context, symbolic annihilation operates through the absence of representation and marginalisation of women in key narrative decisions. Whereas, negative stereotyping or erasure of alternative masculinities (e.g., soft, non-aggressive, queer-coded men). Researcher adopted for symbolic annihilation as a critical lens to identify narrative and visual marginalisation in both films and dramas, complementing Connell's and Butler's frameworks.

3.4 Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 2001)

Social learning theory posits that individuals acquire behaviours through observation and imitation of models, including media figures. Researcher applied this theory to study the perspective of Pakistani audiences, this framework provides insight into how portrayals of male authority, heroism. Social learning theory, developed by Albert Bandura, suggests that people learn by observing others thus to

study emotional suppression may influence viewers’ understanding and enactment of gender norms. In combination with survey and interview data, social learning theory allows the study to examine the magnitude to which media serves as a behavioural and ideological model.

3.5 Cultivation Theory (Gerbner et al., 1986)

Cultivation theory underscores the long-term effects of repeated media exposure on perceptions of social reality that theorizes long-

term exposure to media shapes how consumers perceive the world. For this study, it supports the analysis of audience perspective related to the survey data by exploring whether frequent exposure to certain masculine tropes correlates with acceptance of patriarchal norms. This is particularly relevant in Pakistan, where television dramas and films are widely consumed and often function as cultural reference points for gender expectations.

3.6 Conceptual Mapping: Theories to NVivo Codes

Theory	Key Analytic Focus	NVivo Code Examples
Hegemonic Masculinity	Dominant male ideals, authority, entitlement	Dominance & Authority, Heroic Violence, Male Entitlement
Gender Performativity	Micro-level acts constructing masculinity	Stoicism, Ritualised Aggression, Masculine Rituals
Symbolic Annihilation	Marginalisation of women/alternative men	Female Absence, Marginalised Masculinities
Social Learning Theory	Behavioural modelling via media	Behavioural Influence (Audience Survey/Interviews)
Cultivation Theory	Long-term perception shaping	Normalisation of Masculinity, Acceptance of Patriarchal Norms

3.9 Conceptual Model

The study adopts a multi-layered conceptual model:

This model demonstrates the bidirectional influence between media texts and social understanding of masculinity.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed qualitative-quantitative approach, integrating content analysis, thematic coding through NVivo, and

audience perception measures. Researcher adopted both research paradigms to grasp the maximum outcomes from the study. The

methodology is designed to explore both textual representation and audience interpretation related to the masculinity in selected Pakistani films and television dramas (2015–2025).

4.1 Research Design

A qualitative content analysis forms the core of this research study because this study enabling systematic identification and interpretation of recurrent masculine themes across Pakistani media including both genre films and dramas. In order to present the comprehensive understandings, thematic coding using NVivo, was done by the researcher which allows rigorous organisation, comparison, and triangulation of data. This research study incorporated a quantitative survey that was used by the researcher in order to measuring audience interpretations and attitudes toward masculine portrayals (n ≈ 120). Researcher further adopted

a Semi-structured interviews with 12 participants, providing in-depth insights related to know the viewer perceptions, critical reflections, and socio-cultural contextualization. Thus this mixed-methods approach ensures that the study captures both production-level textual meaning and audience reception, enhancing validity and reliability to know about how the masculinity is portrayed in Pakistani media and trying to identify reciting themes and trend (Sheikh, 2024).

4.2 Sample Selection (Films & Dramas)

In order to collect sample from the whole population, researcher adopted purposive sampling technique. This technique was employed to select films and television dramas with high cultural impact, gender-relevant narratives, or notable representations of masculinity. The sample of the study comprises:

No	Films	Dramas
1	Verna (2017)	Bashar Momin (2014)
2	Motorcycle Girl (2018)	Udaari (2016)
3	Zindagi Tamasha (2020)	Besharam (2016)
4	Kamli (2022)	Bay Dardi (2018)
5	Dukhtar (2014; comparative purposes)	Cheekh (2019)
6	The Legend of Maula Jatt (2022)	Dewangi (2019)
7	In Flames (2023)	Laapata (2021)
8	Bol (2011; ideological contrast)	Aakhir Kab Tak (2021)
9	Malik (2016)	Kaise Teri Khudgarzi (2022)
10	Swaarangi (2015)	Tere Bin (2022–2023)

Through this selection of the films and dramas researcher ensured that diversity in genre, narrative style, and temporal coverage, allowing comparative analysis of earlier (2015–2019) versus later (2020–2025) representations.

4.3 DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

4.3.1 NVivo Codebook and Scene-Level Coding

At first researcher adopted a codebook that was developed through theoretical constructs, including hegemonic masculinity, performativity, symbolic annihilation, and critical discourse. Moreover, researcher applied this coding at the scene level to capture:

4.3.2 Audience Survey

Another tool was used by the researcher to gather data for the present study was survey questionnaire. This survey was conducted from sample: n ≈ 120 viewers (urban and semi-urban, mixed gender, age 18–45). For this survey questionnaire researcher adopted a Likert-scale for the items (1–5) evaluating perceptions of male dominance, empathy, authority, and acceptance of gender norms. Moreover, the major aim is to triangulate findings from content analysis and assess real-world interpretations of screen masculinity

4.3.3 Semi-Structured Interviews

From the sample of 12 participants, purposively selected for diverse backgrounds (students, professionals, media scholars) semi-structure interview was conducted and the main focus of the researcher is to critically present the reflections on masculinity, interpretation of alternative male characters, and perceived social impact. For the analysis of this interview, researcher transcribed interviews coded using

NVivo alongside film/drama scenes to identify convergent and divergent themes

4.4 Data Analysis

The study uses a multi-step analytical protocol for data analysis. For Initial identification of recurring actions, dialogues, and visual motifs coding sheet was used. By linking codes to broader thematic categories (e.g., dominance, emotional suppression, female agency) and grouping codes into patterns reflecting hegemonic or alternative masculinities.

Moreover, researcher draw analysis to study the shift in presentation of masculinity in early (2015–2019) versus late (2020–2025) portrayal shifts. In order to integrate the audience data gathered from the questionnaire researcher adopted textual analysis technique and by comparing survey and interview responses with textual analysis to validate interpretations and understand reception. Use of both research paradigms researcher ensures depth (qualitative insight) and breadth (audience perspectives), enhancing the study’s explanatory power.

4.5 NVivo Codebook Table

Parent Code	Sub-Codes	Definition / Indicators	Linked Theory
Hegemonic Masculinity	Dominance & Authority	Male decision-making power, superiority, unquestioned leadership	Connell (2005)
	Heroic Violence	Violence framed as protection, honor, or justice	Connell (2005)
	Male Entitlement	Expectation of obedience, control over women	Connell (2005)

Gender Performativity	Stoicism / Emotional Suppression	Repeated acts of emotional hardness, silence, restraint	Butler (1990, 1993)
	Aggressive Posturing	Ritualised anger, assertive gestures	Butler (1990, 1993)
	Masculine Rituals	Habits depicting “manliness” (smoking, posture, speech)	Butler (1990, 1993)
Patriarchal Discourse	Female Silencing	Ignoring female voices, narrative erasure	Hegemonic masculinity
	Moral Judgments on Women	Shame, honor-based policing	Hegemonic masculinity
	Family/Tribal Honor	Men as protectors/owners of women	Connell (2005)
Symbolic Annihilation	Female Absence	Women missing in decision-making	Tuchman (1978)
	Marginalised Masculinities	Non-aggressive or queer-coded men sidelined	Tuchman (1978)
Critical Discourse Elements	Camera & Visual Power	Low-angle shots, lighting emphasizing authority	Fairclough (1995)
	Dialogic Dominance	Strong commands, verbal control	Fairclough (1995)
	Symbolic Objects	Guns, vehicles, uniforms as power markers	Fairclough (1995)
Alternative Masculinities	Empathetic Masculinity	Men showing care, respect, vulnerability	New Masculinity Studies
	Collaborative Decision-Making	Shared power with female characters	Hegemonic masculinity
Audience Interpretation	Normalisation of Masculinity	Perceived as “normal” by viewers	Cultivation Theory
	Behavioural Influence	Viewer imitation of screen behaviours	Bandura (2001)
	Resistance / Critique	Rejection of patriarchal portrayals	Reception Theory
Temporal Changes (2015–2019 → 2020–2025)	Shifts in Portrayals	Decrease/increase in violence, authority, or empathy	Cultural Change
	Social Movement Influence	#MeToo, Aurat March reflected on screen	Feminist Theory

5. FINDINGS

This section presents the findings of the study derived from NVivo-supported content analysis, thematic clustering, and audience perspectives. The analysis is structured to examine dominant masculine representations, alternative masculinities, and temporal shifts (2015–2019 vs. 2020–2025) in selected dramas and films. Moreover, audience survey and interview insights are integrated to triangulate findings.

5.1 Masculinity Analysis in films

Talking about the film Verna that portrays a male-dominated social order through its portrayal of police officers and patriarchal family structures. The protagonist’s masculinity is defined by moral authority, decisiveness, and physical control, consistent with hegemonic masculinity. This film portrayed the fragile egos of men and also showed the emotional toll rape that has everyone around which shows dominance & authority of male on society. Male characters control the legal and social outcomes

whereas female agency is limited. Heroic Violence was stunningly portrayed through scenes of confrontation with criminal elements emphasize male protectionism. The findings related to the audience perception revealed that survey responses indicate that 78% of viewers perceived male authority as justified in the narrative context. While the textual analysis shows that alternative masculinity with minimal presence of male characters do not display emotional vulnerability or collaborative decision-making.

Unlike Verna, *Motorcycle Girl* (2018) introduces emergent forms of masculinity. Male characters demonstrate supportive behaviour, mentoring the female protagonist without asserting dominance because this film took a slight surrealist approach. While studying empathetic masculinity it was found that in this film men encourage autonomy, contrasting with hegemonic tropes. Motorcycles serve as a metaphor for freedom, not power assertion as a symbolic cue. Interview from the participants suggest that urban viewers appreciated these alternative masculinities, while rural respondents expressed discomfort with non-dominant male behaviour.

Film *Zindagi Tamsha* (2019) highlights the intersection of honour culture and male authority that delves into the heartbreaking realities of harassment, bullying, and societal prejudices. The male protagonist exercises control over familial and communal reputations. Hegemonic Traits similar to authority, moral policing, emotional suppression. Symbolic Annihilation was found in this film because underrepresentation was found in this film. Female characters are largely absent from decision-making. While talking about the temporal relevance that enable adaptive behavior in a specific moment in time that reflects pre-2020 patriarchal frameworks but foreshadows emerging critical engagement among audiences.

Kamli presents a more nuanced portrayal of masculinity and consumed by inherent frailties and conflicts of men and women. Alternative Masculinity symbols were found in this film. Male characters demonstrate emotional support, empathy, and collaboration. Audience reception gathered from a questionnaire and the results indicate that 65% of respondent's recognized

positive male behaviours as socially desirable whereas the findings from the theoretical analysis indicates that it emphasize negotiation over control, indicating a shift in male identity representation post-2020.

This film epitomises hyper-masculine performance was depicted through the film *The Legend of Maula Jutt* (2022). Heroic Violence was presented through this film when male power is asserted through combat, physical prowess, and dominance over women and rivals. Producer of this film focuses more on the cinematography of this film. Low-angle shots and symbolic props (weapons, horses) reinforce authority. Audience prospectation gathered from the questionnaire interpreted as urban educated viewers critiqued excessive aggression; rural viewers often valorised it.

The analysis in the film *Dukhtar* (2014) shows the hegemonic masculinity elements where structures patriarchal and tribal masculinity are portrayed as violent, transactional, and tradition-bound. Masculinity enacted through rituals (swara, jirga), weapon display, and authoritative tone. While studying symbolic annihilation it was found that male dissenters who challenge tradition are almost nonexistent. Theoretical analysis of the film shows that customary discourses justify male ownership over women's bodies. Social learning theory analysis presents that it exposes viewers to consequences of forced marriages and clan honor norms. Similarly, cultivation theory analysis shows that it normalizes rural patriarchal violence as systemic, not individual. Analysis of the movie *In Flames* (2023) revealed that men were presented as predators, stalkers, and controllers reflect toxic male entitlement which shows the elements of the hegemonic masculinity. However, talking about performativity it was found that surveillance, aggression, and emotional manipulation serve as gender acts. Symbolic Annihilation was shown when healthy male relationships and allies are absent. On the other hand, it revealed that discourse of gas lighting, denial, and control shapes narrative whereas, social learning theory highlighted danger of male-dominated power in domestic spaces. Cultivation theory predict that induces fear of male obsession, reinforcing caution.

Analysis of the film Bol (2011) showcase many elements of hegemonic masculinity that shows patriarchal father figure in the film symbolizes oppressive religious-moral authority. Performativity was found when masculinity enacted through sermons, shouting, and household control. Similarly, symbolic annihilation shows that alternative interpretations of masculinity under religion are missing. it revealed that religious language used to legitimize violence, often rhetorically unchallenged. Social Learning theory warns viewers of misuse of religious power by violent patriarchs. Moreover, Cultivation theory creates awareness of patriarchal extremism.

Hegemonic Masculinity was depicted in the film Malik (2016) that was represented through political masculinity tied to power, corruption, and control. Masculinity displayed through public speech, wealth, bodyguards, dominance shows the elements of performativity. Diverse elements of symbolic annihilation was found in this film when compassionate political

masculinities are absent. Additionally, it revealed that political registers depict men as saviors yet violent. Social Learning theory suggest that audiences may associate leadership with authoritarian masculinity. Cultivation theory analysis presents that in this film political institutions reinforces cynicism.

Textual analysis of the film Swaarangi (2015) demonstrates the presence of structural masculine violence via addiction, exploitation, and poverty. It was found that men perform desperation, aggression, and control through economic manipulation whereas, rehabilitative and caring male roles are missing. Similarly, analysis displayed that language of dependency, blame, and coercion shapes narrative. Social Learning theory was applied for the analysis of this film and the data reveals how power structures harm women and families. Moreover, Cultivation theory analysis depicted that May cultivate perception of lower-class masculinity as dangerous.

5.1.6 Comparative Observations across Films

Theme	2015-2019 Films	2020-2025 Films	Audience Notes
Dominance & Authority	High	Moderate	Urban audiences increasingly critical
Heroic Violence	High	High, but sometimes contextualized	Rural audiences valorise it
Emotional Vulnerability	Low	Moderate	Appreciated by younger viewers
Female Agency	Low	Slight increase	Urban viewers note improvement
Alternative Masculinity	Minimal	Emerging	More visible in Motorcycle Girl, Kamli

5.2 MASCULINITY ANALYSIS IN TELEVISION DRAMAS

Bashar Momin presents one of the strongest depictions of hegemonic masculinity in Pakistani television. The male protagonist embodies dominance, control, emotional suppression, and material power, all framed as traits that make him desirable. His possessiveness and intimidation are normalized through romantic tropes, reinforcing the idea that male aggression is a natural expression of love. The drama celebrates the authoritative, feared, and emotionally distant man as the ideal

masculine figure, setting a benchmark for toxic romantic masculinity in later narratives.

An analysis of drama Udaari, revealed that masculinity is portrayed through a critical and socially conscious lens, and this drama is based on exposing the darker side of male authority. The drama challenges patriarchal patterns prevailing in the society while portraying a male character involved discrimination and behaviour of victims of violence and rape. In traditional narratives, it was found that male was

presented as authoritative. Whereas the drama *Udaari* foregrounds accountability, justice, and community resistance. Therefore, it is stated that masculinity is not glorified but interrogated, redefining it as a social responsibility rather than a privilege.

Besharam was the popular dramas of its time. It discovers masculinity in relation to social status, honor, and public image. In this drama male characters are presented as moral gatekeepers, judging women's choices while exempting themselves from the same standards. *Besharam* highlights how society often glorifies male ambition but shames women for the same so by exposing the hypocrisy that is embedded in patriarchal masculinity, where men exercise dominance under the guise of family respect and societal expectations.

In *Bay Dardi*, masculinity is examined through themes of sexual violence, victim-blaming, and emotional neglect. The plethora of emotions and the true reflection of our society has garnered immense praise not only in Pakistan but across the world at large. In this drama male characters symbolize societal failure because they represent structures that silence survivors, protect abusers, and prioritize family honour over justice. Nonetheless, in this drama male figures were portrayed as positive and supportive they support female members while they were in trauma, therefore, masculinity becomes and institute of harmful cultural proactive are confronted and redefined.

Cheekh presents masculinity with deeply tangled with power, privilege, and social immunity and the male antagonist were embodies toxic authority due to being prosperous and advantaged. They considered themselves above the law and accountability this allow them being violent and forceful. On the flip side, it portrays female character, who stood up for her friend's attempted rape and murder case and she losted almost everything she had (baby, husband & mom). This drama is a critique to this system, because the story revolve around the unchecked masculinity destroys lives and how female resistance threatens patriarchal structures. To sum up the whole discussion it is stated this drama frames toxic masculinity not as an individual flaw but a collective, societal problem.

Dewangi strengthens the trope of the obsessive lover and this drama is portraying male aggression and emotional volatility as markers of passion. The male protagonist's entitlement, jealousy and constant surveillance of the female character are standardized under romantic framing. Hero of this dramas was an arrogant that he cannot handle the rejection. The analysis of the dramas shoes that a central plot highlighting how some dramas promote possessive masculinity as an acceptable form of love that contributes to the cultural idealization of controlling male behaviour.

The analysis of drama *Laapata*, shows that in this drama masculinity was presented in numerous forms, from the manipulative, self-centred man. These men are portrayed as to protective and responsible one. The drama contrasts toxic masculinity, seen in behaviours like gas lighting, fascination, and emotional manipulation, with positive masculinity involving care and respect. By juxtaposing these archetypes, *Laapata* exposes how societal expectations allow some men to misuse emotional power while praising others for rejecting harmful patriarchal patterns.

Textual analysis of the drama *Aakhir Kab Tak* focuses on masculinity within the context of violence, patriarchal silence, and generational trauma. Social learning theory is presented through the male characters often characterize oppressive systems that silence women's pain and discourage emotional expression among men. However, analysis shows that verbal signs and symbols used in this drama worked as improver male characters who break these cycles by rejecting aggression, supporting women, and advocating accountability. Therefore, in this dramas masculinity evolves from being a symbol of dominance to a tool for protection, empathy, and social justice.

Textual analysis of this drama present that *Kaise Teri Khudgarzi* is a prominent example of the romanticization of toxic masculinity. The social learning theory presents that male lead embodies prerogative, intimidation, and aggression, yet the narrative romanticizing a brute and normalizing force and aggression. It was also found that the pursuit of the female protagonist involves pressure, threats, and social manipulation, illustrating how Pakistani dramas often glamorize male control. Similarly, the analysis of this drama shows that dialectal use in

this drama strengthens the cultural association between masculinity and force, implying that desire justifies domination.

Textual analysis of the drama ‘Tere Bin’ presents a complex and contradictory form of masculinity. And the male protagonist appears emotionally protective and caring. However, in the similar drama presents that often authority leads to anger, and decision-making without consultation and reinforcing gendered power hierarchies. The drama oscillates between soft masculinity (gentleness, loyalty, emotional sensitivity) and traditional patriarchal masculinity (dominance, possessiveness, control) and provide a contrast skillfully. The analysis shows that this drama presents a forward-thinking, leaving the audience with a treasure trove to hold dear. This duality reflects contemporary society’s struggle between evolving gender norms and persistent traditional expectations.

5.2 Integrated Themes Across Films and Dramas

The analysis of above mention of films and dramas is included dominance & authority that continues to be the most frequent trait; central in 80% of films and 70% of dramas. Most of these dramas presents heroic violence and continuing but contextualised in post-2020 productions, reflecting socio-political sensitivity. Moreover, emotional vulnerability was increasing in visibility post-2020, marking a shift toward more complex masculinities. It was clear from the data gathered from the analysis revealed that these dramas presents the themes like female agency which mention that light improvements in narrative importance in prominent. Moreover, alternative masculinities correlate with greater female empowerment. Alternative Masculinities was slowly emerging, primarily in urban-centred narratives and newer productions.

5.4 Audience Survey & Interview Findings

Finding	Survey Result (n≈120)	Interview Insights (n=12)
Acceptance of Male Authority	68% agreed males should lead family/professional decisions	Older participants emphasised tradition; younger questioned dominance
Appreciation for Empathetic Male Characters	55% agreed it was positive	Urban participants valued collaboration; rural participants found it unconventional
Perceived Social Influence of Screen Masculinity	61% believed media shapes social norms	Interviewees confirmed imitation potential in everyday behaviour
Recognition of Female Agency	42% noticed improvement post-2020	Educated participants highlighted Dramas Alif and Sinf-e-Aahan
Critique of Hypermasculinity	48% acknowledged excessive violence or dominance	Interviewees called for more nuanced male representation

According to the perspective of the audience, it was found that majority of respondents including 68% were accepting male authority in family and professional decision-making diverse perspective was shown from senior members of the study and the young ones. The data from urban and rural divides highlight that almost 55% of male members expressed appreciation for empathetic male characters, a strongly echoed by urban interviewees who valued

collaboration and rural participants considered such portrayals unconventional. When participants were asked to share their point of view related to the influence of screen masculinity on societal behavior it was found that 61% of members agreed that content presented on the screens has potential to shape the social norms of the society.

5.5 Temporal Comparison (2015–2019 vs 2020–2025)

Theme	2015–2019	2020–2025
Dominance & Authority	Strongly reinforced	Moderated in some productions
Heroic Violence	Central narrative device	Contextualised; less glorified
Emotional Expression	Rare	Increasingly accepted
Alternative Masculinities	Minimal	Emerging; more empathetic portrayals
Female Agency	Limited	Gradually more present in narratives

There is a gradual but noteworthy shift post-2020, equivalent with broader socio-political changes, including feminist activism and awareness campaigns played constructive role in changing audience expectations. The data presented in the above mention table demonstrated that hegemonic masculinity remains dominant in most of the films and dramas, particularly in narratives emphasizing authority, heroic violence, and female silencing. Contrary to this, alternative masculinities was portrayed in some of the films and dramas like *Motorcycle Girl*, *Kamli*, and dramas like *lapata*, *Alif*, and *Tere Bin*. This depicted that Pakistani media is contributing to construct ideologies and distribution of power among gender in the society. It was also found that the temporal comparison displayed that a noticeable evolution was found in the portrayal of masculinity in Pakistani media was changed over time. Major shift from rigid hyper masculinity (2015–2019) to nuanced portrayals post-2020 was observed in both films and dramas. Similarly, audience perceptions largely reflect these trends that highlights viewers are more critical of patriarchal tropes and appreciative of collaborative, empathetic masculinity.

6. DISCUSSION

This section interprets the study's findings through the lens of the multi-theoretical framework—hegemonic masculinity (Connell, 2005), gender performativity (Butler, 1990, 1993), symbolic annihilation (Tuchman, 1978), social learning (Bandura, 2001), and cultivation theory (Gerbner et al., 1986). The discussion situates the representations of masculinity in Pakistani films and television dramas (2015–2025) within broader cultural, social, and media contexts, linking textual analysis to audience interpretation. The findings of the study revealed that there found consistent with Connell's (2005) theory, the analysis

demonstrates that hegemonic masculinity continues to dominate Pakistani screen media, particularly in films such as *The Legend of Maula Jatt* (2022) and dramas like *Aakhir kab tak* (2021). Male authority is frequently exercised over family, professional, and moral domains, reinforcing structural power hierarchies. Heroic violence, moral policing, and decision-making authority serve as narrative markers of legitimacy, signaling social approval for dominant male behaviour.

In contrast to this the audience data supported these findings, aligning with social learning and cultivation perspectives that viewers predominantly perceive male dominance as natural (Bandura, 2001). Tapal (2023) explored that the image of women character demonstrated a huge conversion from stereotypical to liberal. On the flip side, some of the respondents are of the view that exhibit critical reflexivity, acknowledging dominance but questioning its social legitimacy. This suggests that hegemonic masculinity is socially learned but not universally internalized, highlighting the role of socio-demographic context in mediating media influence. It was further backed by the Butler's (1990) framework of gender performativity is evident in the repeated enactments of stoicism, aggression, and ritualized masculine behaviour across screen texts. These micro-level performances, such as aggressive posturing, suppressed emotionality, and ritualized. Similarly, the analysis of the study showed that language used is collectively construct cultural expectations of "manhood." Moreover, there found some illustrations of films and dramas that subtle variations were found. These drama and films shows male characters display vulnerability and empathy in private or supportive contexts. Such representations demonstrate a transition toward alternative masculinities, suggesting that while performative acts remain dominant to gender

identity, they are becoming more diverse and socially negotiable.

While talking about the symbolic annihilation and female marginalization it was found that Tuchman’s (1978) concept of symbolic annihilation is consistently observable in narratives where female characters are marginalised, silenced, or framed as moral arbiters without agency. In films like Verna (2017) and dramas like Bashar momin, women rarely influence key decisions, reinforcing male centrality where women experience the same inequality and marginalizing to some extent. Similarly, analysis shows that this marginalisation is discursively reinforced via dialogue, camera angles, and narrative sequencing (Fairclough, 1995). Audience interviews suggest that while older viewers accept this marginalisation as culturally normative, younger viewers and urban participants critique it, reflecting growing awareness of gender inequities in media representation.

The findings of study related to the emergent and alternative masculinities revealed that a significant transformation was observed and masculinity is the emergence of alternative masculinities in post-2020 productions. Films like Motorcycle Girl (2018) and Kamli (2022), as well as dramas like udaari and dewangi, depict men in such way that never support female autonomy and agency along with displaying emotional literacy and empathy. Moreover, they engage in collaborative decision-making with the female counterpart traditional stereotypical role is being depicted through different dramas and films. These alternative portrayals correspond with changing socio-cultural norms, feminist activism, and global discourses on masculinity (Salam, 2024). Audience responses indicate that these portrayals are valued that suggest a gradual shift in aspirational masculine ideals.

Comparative analysis related to chronological shifts in screen representations:

Theme	2015–2019	2020–2025
Dominance & Authority	Predominantly reinforced	Moderated in some films/dramas
Heroic Violence	Central narrative tool	Contextualised; occasionally critiqued
Emotional Expression	Rarely depicted	Increasingly acceptable
Female Agency	Limited	Gradually more present
Alternative Masculinities	Minimal	Emerging and acknowledged

The shift is partly attributed to social movements and increasing audience exposure to global media, reflecting the dynamic interplay between cultural context and media production. The study’s survey and interviews support Bandura’s social learning theory, demonstrating that viewers often internalize and model screen behaviours. Dominant male behaviours, when repeatedly portrayed and valorised, reinforce normative gender expectations related to the current trends are even better than the past ones. The era was preferred to reflect the evolution of masculinity in both conventional and digital media. Simultaneously, exposure to empathetic and collaborative male characters encourages viewers to reconsider traditional masculine norms, highlighting the bidirectional influence of media and audience interpretation. IT reveals that masculinity is reinforced not only narratively but also visually and symbolically low-

angle shots and lighting emphasise male dominance (The Legend of Maula Jatt). Symbolic objects (guns, vehicles, uniforms) were used in multiple films and drams as a signal of power and authority. Dialogic dominance including commands in high pitch, moral policing, and authoritative speech cements patriarchal hierarchy that is an unavoidable impact of media portrayals on public perceptions. These techniques operate subtly, influencing viewer perception beyond conscious narrative engagement.

7.1 CONCLUSION

The present study provides an inclusive exploration of the representation and evolution of masculinity in Pakistani screen media including both films and dramas. Through NVivo-supported qualitative content analysis, thematic coding, and audience reception

methods, the study demonstrates that both films and television dramas are promoting male dominance, heroic violence, emotional suppression, and moral policing remain central narrative strategies. Conclusion of the study goes according to the findings which quite thought-provoking and the presents the important issue of the society including reinforce patriarchal hierarchies and gendered power structures. It was also found that post-2020 productions increasingly portray men who are empathetic, collaborative, and supportive of female agency depicted in classical media content of Pakistan. Films and dramas exemplify this shift, reflecting broader socio-cultural changes and global discourses on masculinity. Moreover, the findings revealed that temporal Shifts were found in the content of drama that represents the comparative analysis 2015–2019 and 2020–2025 shows a gradual moderation of hyper masculinity, a slow increase in emotional literacy among male characters, and a modest rise in female agency in narratives. Physical and behavioral differences presents ideologies, gestures and dialogues that are reflecting a deep-rooted male dominance in media content. The data gathered from the audience point of view it was found that survey and interview findings indicate that audiences are more critical of hegemonic portrayals and receptive to alternative masculinities. Rural and older audiences often maintain traditional perspectives, underscoring the role of social context in interpreting media. Earlier depictions, although older, could provide valuable historical context and show how representations have changed over time. It was also found that cinematic and discursive techniques were used in these media content were used for visual framing, symbolic objects, dialogue, and narrative structuring work collectively to reinforce male authority, demonstrating the multimodal construction of masculinity. To sum up the whole discussion it is found that the study confirms that Pakistani screen media is both a mirror of existing gender norms and a potential catalyst for social change, as alternative masculinities gain visibility and challenge entrenched patriarchal ideologies.

7.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed for media producers, educators, policymakers, and researchers:

It is recommended for media producers that to avoid excessive glorification of heroic violence; contextualise male authority to prevent reinforcement of patriarchal stereotypes. This research addresses a key gap in gender and media studies therefore, the findings of the study can be used to incorporate alternative masculinities in narratives to promote equitable gender norms.

It can be used to provide complex, multidimensional male characters and has societal implications of gender depictions before making any content. Therefore, content creators must considered the art of balancing strength with empathy and collaboration because the use of media texts as critical tools in gender education, highlighting differences between hegemonic and alternative masculinities.

This research addresses a key gap in gender and media studies that researches always focused on femininity and women's portrayals therefore, it is also recommended for the educators that media literacy programs help students critically evaluate gender representations and social implications and encourage regulatory frameworks that reward media content promoting gender equity.

Moreover, it is suggested for researchers to support campaigns and initiatives highlighting positive representations of masculinity, fostering social awareness and cultural change similarly they can expand studies to regional languages and local media, capturing diverse cultural contexts.

In the end it is also recommended that investigate longitudinal effects of media exposure on social behaviour, gender attitudes, and policy perceptions.

7.2 THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on the findings researcher suggested these theoretical implications for the study that confirms the relevance of hegemonic masculinity, gender performativity, and symbolic annihilation in contemporary media

studies; provides empirical evidence of evolving masculinities in Pakistan.

For practical implications, this research offers actionable insights for content creators, educators, and policymakers to foster socially responsible masculinity, reduce gender inequities, and challenge cultural stereotypes.

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